

Tracing Genre Pedagogy: From Bakhtin's Utterance Theory to Halliday and Swales in EFL Writing Instruction

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Abstract

Finding effective approaches to teaching writing remains a persistent challenge for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) university professors. In response, Genre Writing Pedagogy (GWP) has emerged as a promising framework, emphasizing the functional use of language within specific social and disciplinary contexts. Drawing on Bakhtin's notion of sub-genres, as well as theoretical contributions from Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics and Swales' Move Analysis, this paper explores how genre theory informs the teaching of academic writing in higher education. It argues for the importance of equipping students with the linguistic and rhetorical tools needed to communicate effectively within their fields of study. The paper concludes by presenting a sample lesson that illustrates how GWP can be applied in the writing classroom.

Keywords: *Genre writing pedagogy, EFL writing, Bakhtin utterance, Halliday SFL, Swale moves.*

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Introduction

Identifying effective strategies for teaching writing and empowering students to enhance their writing skills remains a significant concern for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) university professors. Consequently, researchers in EFL writing have consistently sought innovative approaches to address the challenges faced by both writing teachers and students. One such approach is the implementation of Genre Writing Pedagogy (GWP).

Grounded in the principle that language is learned to serve specific purposes within particular social contexts, GWP emphasizes engaging students in learning activities and language use that equip them with the linguistic tools needed to effectively interact within their academic and professional communities. Accordingly, it is recommended that students in the sciences learn the language specific to their discipline, while

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students in the arts acquire the language relevant to their field. Furthermore, within both science and art disciplines, there is a strong need for students to understand the distinct linguistic features of their respective sub-disciplines.

The development of this pedagogical approach is inspired by Bakhtin's argument that every genre contains sub-genres worthy of study and analysis. Building on this view, genre theorists have suggested that teaching students the language required to communicate effectively within their specific fields can help overcome barriers to learning how to write well. In this context, the present paper explores Bakhtin's argument for the significance of sub-genres within genres, and how scholars such as Halliday and Swales have drawn on this idea to enhance the teaching and learning of writing. In light of this discussion, the paper concludes by proposing a sample lesson plan that applies Genre Writing Pedagogy in the teaching of writing.

Bakhtin on Genre

The term *genre* has long been associated with traditional literary categories, such as the novel, the poem, the tragedy, and / or the sermon. This literary conception had dominated scholarly discourse until the emergence of alternative perspectives in the 20th century, most notably with the work of **Mikhail Bakhtin**. In his influential essay "*The Problem of Speech Genres*" (1986), Bakhtin challenged the limited view of genre as purely literary, and instead theorized that genres are fundamental to all "diverse areas of human activity (which) involves the use of language" (p. 60). Thus, he introduced the concept of **"speech genres" in reference to the** relatively stable types of utterances¹ shaped by specific social and communicative contexts.

According to Bakhtin, the prevailing scholarly emphasis on secondary genres (novels, dramas, or philosophical dissertations) was limited in that it overlooked the role of primary speech genres embedded within them. These primary genres, which arise from everyday communicative situations such as conversations, letters, and spontaneous exchanges, serve as the foundational building blocks of more complex secondary genres. For instance, a novel, while considered a secondary genre, oftentimes incorporates a range of primary genres within it. For instance, characters may engage in dialogue, exchange letters, or deliver monologues. Each of these may reflect distinct speech genres drawn from and useful in particular cases of social life.

This layering of genres contributes to what Bakhtin termed dialogism, which is the interaction of multiple voices and perspectives within a single text or, in simpler terms, dialogues in action. Examples of dialogism might equally include a dialogue between, for instance, two students engaged in a conversation about the worth of AI in education and a writer positioning the ideas of different scholars among others to establish a negotiation of perspectives in their texts. Such a view challenges the rigid boundaries traditionally imposed on genres and emphasizes their inherently social, interactive, and dynamic nature. Failing to account for the context-dependent nature of these primary forms leads to an incomplete understanding of how meaning is constructed in language, and, thus, in real life situations.

Bakhtin's emphasis on the significance of primary speech genres is important in several key ways. First, it highlights the fundamentally social and contextual nature of language. This emphasizes the fact that meaning is not constructed in isolation but through habitual, patterned interactions in everyday life. Primary genres, such as greetings, complaints, questions, or casual narratives, are not merely simple forms of

communication; they are deeply embedded in the cultural and institutional practices of everyday communication. Second, Bakhtin's distinction between primary and secondary genres offers a layered understanding of discourse, wherein complex texts are seen as composites of more basic communicative forms. This insight is crucial for pedagogy, as it implies that mastering sophisticated academic or literary writing requires familiarity with the conventions of these foundational genres. Third, by foregrounding the dialogic nature of language, Bakhtin situates genre not as a fixed structure, but as a dynamic response to prior utterances and expected replies, making genre inherently interactive and evolving. These contributions laid the groundwork for later theories—such as Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) and Swales' CARS model.

The exploration of utterance, as argued by Bakhtin, is conducted from within the context it is delivered and/or received. That is, an utterance does not exist in isolation. Instead, it is commonly shaped by, and responsive to, the specific social, historical, and communicative context in which it occurs. For Bakhtin, understanding an utterance requires considering who is speaking, to whom, for what purpose, in what situation, and with what prior discourse in mind. For example, the phrase *"That's great"* may carry entirely different meanings depending on context:

- If said in response to good news, it expresses genuine approval.
- If said sarcastically after hearing about a problem (e.g., "The finals were delayed again." "That's great."), it may signal frustration or irony other than being glad to hear of the exam being delayed again.

Bakhtin's observations regarding the presence of primary genres within secondary genres have resonated deeply with both language theorists and applied linguists. If texts, be they primary or secondary sources, can incorporate genres originating from distinct spheres of communication, it stands to reason that such texts allow genre-sensitive analyses. Moreover, these texts offer valuable openings for language teaching and learning, especially when grounded in the sociocultural context of the learners' community. Thus, genre-based perspectives on language teaching have emerged; perspectives that this article explores specifically through the lens of genre writing pedagogy in an EFL context.

Genre Writing Pedagogy in EFL

Bakhtin's argument that secondary genres embed primary genres has drawn considerable attention from linguists. The notion that a secondary genre - such as the novel - can incorporate primary genres like letters, conversations, or sermons suggests that language pedagogy could, and arguably should, be approached through the lens of primary and secondary genres. This perspective opens up valuable possibilities for teaching and learning language by anchoring instruction in authentic communicative practices. Such Authenticity both originates from and mirrors the communicative conventions shared and maintained by members of a language-using community.

This, in turn, means that - particularly in relation to the focus of this article - the effective teaching and learning of writing, both in general and within EFL contexts, should align lesson outcomes and delivery with the communicative conventions, primary utterances, of the communities to which learners belong or are expected to belong. For example, biology students should be introduced to the primary genres relevant to their field of study, while applied linguistics students need exposure to the

foundational genre characteristics of language research and analysis. These genres not only reflect the discourse practices of the scientific community but also serve as foundational requisites of the broader, secondary utterances of the community, wherein they may belong later. The next section explores how linguists have made use of Bakhtin's remarks about genres to develop an innovative pedagogical approach to the teaching and learning of writing. The focus, however, will be on Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics and Swales' rhetorical moves.

SFL aims to establish an analytical framework that elucidates the relationship between language and social structure (Halliday & Hasan, 1985). Halliday conceptualizes linguistics as a set of systems designed to generate meanings in specific social contexts; thus, the focus is on how language functions as a medium of communication rather than on the grammatical rules governing its structures (Hyland, 2004). According to Halliday and Matthiessen (2014), understanding a language entails grasping its functions within social situations and identifying the rules governing its usage within those contexts. For instance, the grammar, vocabulary, and style employed in writing a formal letter differ from those used in writing an informal letter. Halliday and Hasan (1985) term this relationship between texts and their contexts as Generic Structure Potential.

This plays a pivotal role in enabling language users to anticipate the structural features permissible within a given text to suit a specific context. For such an end, Halliday and Hasan (1985, as cited in Sunday & Fagunleka, 2017) propose several textual components, including (1) mandatory elements, (2) optional elements, (3) the sequence of these elements and whether their arrangement is mandatory or optional, and (4) the frequency of occurrence of each element within the text. Awareness of these components allows, for example, an EFL student to proficiently structure their research papers and/or a researcher to effectively organize their articles. In essence, Eggins (1994) succinctly summarizes the key elements of SFL exposition:

common to all systemic linguists is an interest in how people use language with each other in accomplishing everyday social claims about language: that language use is functional; that its function is to make meanings; that these meanings are influenced by the social and cultural context in which they are exchanged and that the process of using language is a semiotic process, a process of making meanings by choosing. (p. 2)

Key to Eggins' understanding of the SFL perspective is its focus on the pragmatic aspects of language use, particularly how individuals employ language to fulfill various social functions in their everyday interactions. Central to this perspective is also the recognition that language serves a functional purpose, namely, to convey meaning. However, this meaning-making process is not isolated; instead, it is deeply interconnected with the social and cultural contexts within which communication occurs. In essence, systemic linguists view language as a dynamic and multifaceted tool that individuals utilize to negotiate social realities. Thus, its significance is shaped by the interplay of linguistic, social, and cultural components.

Halliday (1988) identifies three meta-functions of texts when perceived from an SFL perspective: ideational, interpersonal, and textual. The ideational meta-function concerns how humans perceive the world and the type of ties connecting concepts to things they refer to. It encompasses the representation of extratextual reality, whether within or outside human consciousness, in a text. In simpler terms, the ideational meta-function pertains to the ideas people intend to express through the language they

produce (Banks, 2002). Thus, the primary focus of the ideational meta-function is on how individuals can clearly express ideas for their interlocutors to easily understand.

He distinguishes between two subcategories of Ideational meta-functions, which he names experiential and logical meta-functions. The experiential meta-function refers to the information people convey about the experiences they undergo, while the logical meta-function is concerned with ensuring that incidents are logically connected (Halliday, 1985). Due to the significant interaction between experiential and logical meta-functions, Halliday includes them under the component of the ideational function of texts.

The interpersonal meta-function, as explained by Halliday, serves to establish and maintain social relationships between the parties engaged in a communicative act (speaker-listener; writer-reader). Butt et al. (1995) note that the interpersonal meta-function uses language to convey interaction and indicate the level of commitment or obligation assigned to our proposition or suggestion. Recognizing the significance of this function is essential to communication, which fundamentally relies on intersubjective dialogue (Halliday, 1992).

The third meta-function that language performs, Halliday notes, is textual. At this level, language functions to create a text that articulates abstract thought through a lexicogrammar structure that can be either spoken or written. Halliday further emphasizes that the textual function of a text is what facilitates the realization of the other two meta-functions in the real world. Additionally, Bartlett and O'Grady (2017) suggest that the textual meta-function is realized through the decisions a speaker or writer makes in linking the ideas and reality they wish to convey (ideational), as well as the relationship they aim to establish or develop (interpersonal).

By understanding the meta-functions of language, speakers and writers can choose lexico-grammatical structures that suit the social context in which they are communicating, whether they are creators or recipients of linguistic content. This aspect is particularly relevant to the teaching-learning of EFL writing, as discussed and promoted by the SFL genre writing approach.

Based on the previous discussions, SFL views genre as “the rhetorical structures fundamental to various forms of communication in a culture,” and vivid descriptions of these structures help teachers and students understand and differentiate between the requirements of various genres such as recount, procedure, report, and explanation (Hyland, 2004, p.29). This awareness, Hyland adds, enables teachers to classify texts into groups with similar functions and contexts, understand how to sequence a writing course, raise their students' awareness of the similarities among texts within the same genre, and scaffold students towards independent production of texts that align with their community's genre expectations.

The methodology for teaching and learning genre from an SFL perspective hinges on a crucial component: explicit instruction to introduce the rhetorical and linguistic features recommended by the community for effective writing (Hyland, 2004). This methodology aligns with Lev Vygotsky's (1978) argument that language learners should be provided with material within their Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). The ZPD draws the boundary between what learners can accomplish independently and what they require assistance with from a more knowledgeable individual, such as a teacher or classmate. In essence, Vygotsky's argument suggests that lessons should present a manageable challenge for students, enabling them to learn how to write effectively within their writing communities.

Hyland (2004) proposes a cyclical process to scaffold students through the phases of an SFL writing lesson. First, teachers engage students in the context of the genre using teaching techniques like predicting, brainstorming, and visiting some areas, etc., which clarify the objective of the genre and the social situation(s) where it belongs. Second, students with the help of the teacher explore and model the rhetorical features of the genre in order to be aware of the phases and functions they have. Third, guided practice of the genre is set through activities such as fill-in the gap exercises, acting, matching items or completing sentences, etc. Finally, teachers step back and allow learners to engage in independent writing activities that aim to replicate, as closely as possible, the authentic situations in which such writing is realistically needed.

Nagago (2019) proposes a sample writing lesson designed for both higher and lower proficiency university classes, applying SFL genre theory to the teaching of writing. The objectives of the lesson are: (1) to expose students to the organization and language features of a text. The lesson consists of four main phases: In the first stage, learners analyze the layout and language patterns in a model text provided by the teacher. Next, learners select and analyze an online text similar to the one discussed in class. During stage two, students complete a 50 to 60-minute writing exercise. In stage three, students analyze their classmates' essays, focusing on moves and occurrences of personal pronouns. Additionally, they examine the frequency of modal verbs. Finally, in stage four, learners collectively reflect on the results of their genre analysis.

The bottom line, as Byrnes (2014) indicates, an improved SFL perspective aims at enabling learners to express meanings in a second language and to value lexicogrammar in terms of the connection between culture and texts and the significance of genre. For these to be achieved, teachers begin lessons by helping students know the field; next, they engage them in genre modeling activities; after, they accompany them through joint text production; and finally, individual students produce their texts independently (Derewianka & Jones, 2016).

Rhetorical Moves

A variety of move models have been proposed and applied in the analysis of written texts. Initially, this type of analysis was pioneered by Swales to enhance the understanding of non-native English speakers regarding the rhetorical structure of research articles. Over time, it has been effectively extended to encompass other areas within English for Specific Purposes (ESP) (Upton and Cohen, 2009). Despite its broadening scope, Upton and Cohen explain that move analysis has largely adhered to a framework they summarize as follows.

- Conduction of inter-rater reliability test to check the extent to which the awareness of moves manifests in texts;
- Texts division into moves;
- Clear explanation of how these moves are used in texts;
- Identification of possible further moves after the complete analysis;
- Revision of the findings to overcome issues resulting from the inter-rater test.

This observation does not refute the earlier assertion that move analysis might not adhere to a fixed sequence. Rather, it underscores the predominant framework that ESP analysts and learners should recognize. Following This framework enables them

to discern and comprehend the rhetorical stages that texts within a discourse community typically follow.

Moves can be examined through four levels (Can et al., 2016). Firstly, ‘the range’ perspective investigates the necessity of a move in the writing of a particular discourse community. This involves quantifying the occurrences of moves in at least 100 introductions, abstracts, conclusions, etc. For instance, if a move appears in 60% of the analyzed texts, it is considered essential. However, for a move to be deemed obligatory, it typically needs to occur in 80% of the texts (Swales and Feak, 2009). Secondly, the ‘amount’ perspective identifies the length of written text or its segments. For example, a researcher might analyze the percentage of establishing a niche in the introduction of research articles or dissertations by university students. Thirdly, ‘organization’ analysis focuses on the sequence of sections within the writing of a community. Lastly, move analysis examines the common ‘lexico-grammatical patterns’ in a research paper or its sections, including tenses, modality, and vocabulary.

Originally, Swales’ move analysis (1990) focused on the moves found within research article introductions. It comprises three moves, each consisting of a number of steps: the first is the establishment of the field or territory. The purpose of this step is to demonstrate the significance of the study by highlighting its interest, relevance, importance, and criticality. Three steps are involved at this level:

- Announcing the value of the study and/or highlighting the research problem;
- Providing general information about the topic and/or describing the present status of the phenomena;
- Reflection on the studies that may have partly discussed the topic of the paper.

The second move establishes a valid argument that justifies the need for the research at hand. This could be achieved by identifying a gap, questioning an acknowledged claim, or by furthering previous research. This Move proceeds through :

- Establishing a claim against existing research;
- Developing the research problem in the light of the gap in the literature;
- Asking questions about the limitations of previous research and how the paper will overcome each of them;
- Extending previous research to explain the research problem.

The final move informs about what the study will add to research or the new ways how to see the studied phenomenon compared to the findings of the previous studies. For this end, move three considers :

- An outline of the purpose of the research with a clear explanation of the objectives;
- A response to the “so what?” question;
- A declaration of the main findings;
- A statement of what remains of the paper will be organized.

Swales refers to these moves as “Create a Research Space (CARS);” they are a revised version of his original four move analysis: field creation, previous studies survey, current research presentation, and research concern. The CARS Model has since then been used to analyze not only introductions but other components of research papers

including abstracts (Bhatia, 1997). Not only this, but Swale’s move analysis has also been used to analyze “academic, professional and general genres (Biber et al., 2007).

In some cases, Swale’s move model has been adapted to fit the analytical rationale of authors analyzing students’ dissertations or professional research articles. One example of these adaptations is that of *Rosa Lores-Sanz (2017)*:

Table 1. Framework for Abstract Analysis

Moves	Function	Question asked
Relevance	Setting the scene for the current research (contextualization)	What is known about the current field/topic of research?
Aim	Stating the purpose of the study, research question and/or hypotheses	What is/are the objective(s) of the study?
Gap	Identifying a niche of knowledge, or counter-claiming previous knowledge, or raising a question not answered yet in the literature	What is not known/not clarified in the topic under study?
Method	Describing the materials, subjects, approach, variables, etc.	How was the research done?
Results	Reporting the main findings of the study	What did the research find?
Conclusions /Implications	Interpreting the results/findings and/or drawing implications	What do the results mean? So what?

Source: Rosa Lores-Sanz, 2017

Bhatia (1993) proposes a different model to analyze the moves in abstracts of academic research papers. He identifies four moves a researcher needs to present and briefly discusses in the abstract of his/her paper. These moves, according to Bhatia, provide due information about (1) the conducted research, (2) how it has been done, (3) what has been found, and (4) a conclusion briefing the whole work. In other words, an abstract presents the purpose of the paper, describes the research methodology, summarizes the findings, and closes with a conclusion.

Additionally, Phuong Dzung Pho (2008) highlights five moves research paper abstracts of different disciplines and for multiple purposes have:

Table 2. Framework for Abstract Analysis

Moves	Function/Description	Question Asked
Move 1: Situating the research <STR>	Setting the scene for the current research (topic generalisation)	What has been known about the field/topic of research?
Move 2: Presenting the research <PTR>	Stating the purpose of the study, research questions and/or hypotheses	What is the study about?
Move 3: Describing the methodology <DTM>	Describing the materials, subjects, variables, procedures...	How was the research done?
Move 4: Summarising the findings <STF>	Reporting the main findings of the study	What did the researcher find?
Move 5: Discussing the research <DTR>	Interpreting the results/findings and/or giving recommendations, implications/applications of the study	What do the results mean? So what?

Source: Pho, 2008

Last but not least, Ken Hyland (2000) identifies a list of five moves to analyze abstracts. The first in this list, ‘introduction’, argues for the significance of the research, makes generalizations about the topic, defines the key concepts, and highlights the gap. The second move ‘purpose’ announces the goal and the hypothesis of the whole work. The third move, ‘method’ describes the participants and the resources of data. The fourth, ‘product’, presents what the research has found. The final move, ‘conclusion’, declares the conclusions, assesses the value of the study, declares the limitations, and provides recommendations for further research.

Swale revised the model he proposed in 1990.

Figure 1. Swales' Revised CARS Model

Source: Swales, 1990

According to this model, writers begin by “establishing a territory” for their research, typically through generalizations about the topic. Following this move, writers “establish a niche,” which involves declaring the gap in the literature, expanding on existing knowledge, and justifying the research positively. While the first two steps are obligatory, the last is optional. Then authors proceed to the “occupying of the niche” move, which consists of seven steps, of which only the first step, “announcing present research descriptively and/or purposively,” is obligatory. The others are either optional, probable, or possible in certain types of introductions. The utilization of Swales’ CARS model aims to investigate the extent to which Moroccan MA applied linguistics students are aware of the common rhetorical organization of academic writing. It is worth mentioning that Swales’ CARS is the most common and preferred rhetorical structure for the introduction sections in research papers (Samraj, 2008).

Genre in EFL Writing Instruction

The exploration of writing pedagogy can be meaningfully enriched when approached through the lens of Bakhtin’s genre theory, particularly his distinction between primary and secondary genres. Bakhtin emphasized that genres emerge from specific social and communicative contexts, shaping the way individuals use language in both casual and formal contexts. Building on this perception, scholars such as Halliday and Swales recognized the pedagogical value of identifying and analyzing genres as socially situated forms of discourse. Their work foregrounds the importance of teaching writing not in isolation but in connection with the conventions and communicative purposes of the specific discourse communities to which learners or researchers belong.

This understanding supports the idea that learners should not merely acquire general writing skills but rather develop genre-specific awareness. For instance, a student of applied linguistics would benefit from learning the lexico-grammatical patterns typical of scholarly writing in their field, as emphasized in Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics. At the same time, they may also be taught to recognize and apply the rhetorical moves identified by Swales in academic texts, particularly in research article introductions. By aligning writing instruction with the norms of the academic community, learners become better equipped to participate in the discourses of their field.

Building on the solid connection between Bakhtin's genre theory and Swales' rhetorical move approach, this paper proposes a genre-based writing lesson aimed at teaching EFL students how to write the introduction section of a research article. This lesson not only draws on the CARS (Create a Research Space) model but also reflects Bakhtin's notion that genres are socially situated and dialogic in nature. Accordingly, the lesson is designed to make explicit the rhetorical expectations of academic discourse communities, while encouraging learners to see writing as a purposeful and context-sensitive activity.

Conclusion

Bakhtin's recognition of utterances as autonomous and meaningful units has significantly influenced genre studies, offering new pathways for linguists to rethink the teaching and learning of writing. His perspective shifts the focus from broad, generalized approaches to a more detailed analysis of specific textual components. Consequently, teaching students how to write a full article becomes more effective when its constituent parts are explicitly identified and addressed in writing syllabi. These parts, seen from a Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) perspective, can include features such as phraseology, lexical bundles, and thematic structures; from the viewpoint of rhetorical genre studies, they may encompass the rhetorical moves and steps typical of academic sections such as the abstract, introduction, and literature review. Integrating these insights into writing instruction allows for a more targeted and genre-sensitive pedagogy. For this reason, studies that have clearly highlighted and strongly recommended the integration of genre writing pedagogy (Belbouah & Chibi, 2025; Hyland, 2007). However, as a significant number of studies indicate, the implementation of genre-based writing pedagogy has not gained sufficient interest, particularly in tertiary education - so much so that even students at the graduate level may remain unfamiliar with its principles and practices (Belbouah & Bouguerba, 2025).

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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Appendix

Abstract: Rhetorical Moves

I. Lead In

What does it take to be a painter?

Is this similar or different from **being a writer**?

Are painting and writing natural or learnt skills?

II. Modelling

A. Match the concept to its correct definitions (Choose 2 options):

Rhetorical Moves refer to:

- The specific writing techniques used to create a particular literary style.
- The structural components that guide the organization and flow of a text.
- The persuasive arguments employed within a genre to convince the reader of a particular viewpoint.
- The strategic organization of idea within a genre to achieve specific communicative purposes.

B. Read the text and answer the questions:

Abstract

The abstract found at the beginning of most journal articles has increasingly become an essential part of the article. It tends to be the first part of the article to be read and, to some extent, it 'sells' the article. Acquiring the skills of writing an abstract is therefore important to novice writers to enter the discourse community of their discipline. Based on 30 abstracts from three journals, the present study aims at exploring not only the rhetorical moves of abstracts in the fields of applied linguistics and educational technology, but also the linguistic realizations of moves and authorial stance in different abstract moves. The results show that there are three obligatory moves in abstracts in these two disciplines — *Presenting the research*, *Describing the methodology*, and *Summarizing the results*. The results also indicate that a combination of certain linguistic features such as grammatical subjects, verb tense and voice can help distinguish moves in the abstract. The findings of the study have some pedagogical implications for academic writing courses for graduate students, especially students from non-English backgrounds.

(Pho, 2008)

a. What is the main objective an abstract?

b. What are the aims of this abstract?

.....
.....

.....
.....

c. What are the results of this research?

.....
.....

C. Match each abstract below with the relevant rhetorical framework. Use the table to justify your answer.

Abstract 1

Abstract

^[1]The aims of this paper are to analyze and compare the discourse functions of grammatical subjects used in research article abstracts in the disciplines of Applied Linguistics and Economics. ^[2]The data for this study consisted of 60 research article abstracts published in 2010 and 2011 in the journals of *Applied Linguistics* and *Oxford Economic Papers*. ^[3]The corpus was analyzed using the classification of discourse functions of grammatical subjects established by Gosden. ^[4]The analysis revealed disciplinary differences concerning the discourse functions enacted by the application of the grammatical subject. ^[5]These findings add to the claim that academic writing (research article abstract writing in this study) is shaped by the writer's disciplinary background with particular reference to the use of the grammatical subject as a theme in text development.

Keywords: grammatical subject, discourse function, disciplinary difference, research article abstract, text development

Elshahini, 2015

Abstract 2

Abstract

'Statistics has always been a significant tool at the disposal of the applied linguistics researcher to analyze and interpret data.' In Morocco, however, little is known about applied linguistics doctoral students' level of statistical mastery, and how it shapes their attitudes towards statistics. This study examined 57 doctoral candidates' knowledge of statistics, and explored their attitudes towards statistics employed in applied linguistics research. The study used the statistical literacy questionnaire adapted by Loewen et al. (2014) to measure self-reported knowledge of statistics and students' attitudes. Results showed that the participants are familiar to a large extent with basic descriptive statistics, moderate extent with inferential statistics and to an extremely small extent with advanced statistics. The results also showed that, as beginning researchers, they perceive statistics as an important tool for sound research design. The study suggests some recommendations based on these findings in order to advance quantitative research in the Moroccan doctoral training programs.

Keywords: applied linguistics, doctoral students, statistical knowledge, attitudes

El Hadri & Ghicha, 2022

Rhetorical Frameworks:

Researcher(s)	Year	Moves
Bhatia	1993	Aim/methods/findings/conclusions
Santos	1996	Macro-level/micro-level sentence features
Hyland	2000	Introduction/purpose/method/product/conclusion
Paltridge and Starfield	2007	Main aims, specific objectives, reasons, processes, results
Belcher	2009	Reason/topic/method/results/conclusions/recommendations
Swales, Irwin, and Feak	2009	Situating the research by generalizing the topic, presenting the research, describing the methodology, summarizing the findings, and describing the research by interpreting the results and/or giving recommendations, implications, and applications of the study

Abstract 1: _____	Abstract 2: _____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____
_____	_____

III. Guided Writing

- a. I have used one paragraph to write the abstract. Yes No
- b. The paragraph is not indented. Yes No
- c. I have followed a rhetorical model. Yes No
- d. My abstract is double spaced. Yes No
- e. I included the keywords. Yes No

IV. Independent writing

A. In groups of four, write a hypothetical abstract about an applied linguistics topic to publish in a specialized magazine. Be prepared to argue for your abstract in the presence of a panel of journal editors.

B. Imagine you are a member of a journal panel, use the checklist below to evaluate the abstracts submitted to your Journal.

Editors' Checklist of Abstracts:

- 1. Is the Abstract concise, factual, and to the point? Yes No
- 2. Does the Abstract synthesize the main points of the paper? Yes No
- 3. Are there brief statements on the purpose and scope of the research? Yes No
- 4. Does the Abstract summarize the principal results and major conclusions? Yes No
- 5. Is the abstract between 100 and 250 words? Yes No
- 6. Does the abstract include information about the research methodology? Yes No

Any further comments?

Accept: Yes No

